

COMMON CHICORY-(*CICHORIUM INTYBUS* L.) USEFUL PROPERTIES AND USAGE OF MEDICINAL PLANT

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8200632>

Abstract. *Decrees of the President of Uzbekistan PD- No.3968 dated October 12, 2018 “On measures to regulate the field of folk medicine in the Republic of Uzbekistan”, PD-5707 dated April 10, 2019 “On measures to further develop the pharmaceutical industry of the republic in 2019-2021”. The beneficial properties of agrotechnics of medical plant Common chicory - (*Cichorium intybus* L.) for the protection of human health were studied.*

Keywords: *Common chicory, metabolite, inulin, bifidostimulant, fructose, intibin glycoside, carotene, groups of vitamins B (1, 2, 3), vitamin C, macro and microelements (Na, K, Ca, Mg, P, Fe), tannin, pectin, tar, metabolism, gastritis, dysbacteriosis, dyspepsia, atherosclerosis, tachycardia, hypertension, neurasthenia, depression.*

Introduction. Common chicory -(*Cichorium intybus* L.) A perennial herbaceous plant belonging to the Compositae family. The stem is branched, serbarg, 30-130 cm long, the lower part is white hairy. The leaves are arranged in a row. The flowers are pale, clustered in a short panicle in the axils of the leaves, and collected in a single basket-like inflorescence at the end of the stem. The root is an arrow root. penetrates the soil to a depth of 1.5 m. The root of common chicory contains up to 20% inulin. (It is grown as a medicinal plant in European countries). It begins to grow in March. Blooms and bears fruit from July to October. Grows from seed. Mainly found among irrigated crops. It also grows in abandoned lands, roads, fields, stream banks, and gardens. It is a pest-prone plant. In folk medicine, stem decoction and ash are used to treat sunstroke and rash.

It is widespread in European countries, including Tashkent, Jizzakh, Samarkand, Kashkadarya and Surkhandarya regions of Uzbekistan, and grows on stony and gravelly slopes of the lower and middle mountain regions. The stem is erect and covered with long hairs, the leaves are opposite. The flowers are blue, pink and white, located in inflorescences or in short baskets. Common chicory fruits have the appearance of a prismatic pistachio with a membranous papule.

Common chicory -(*Cichorium intybus* L.) 3-25 thousand seeds can be obtained from one bush of a medicinal plant. There are milk ducts in all organs of the plant. Common chicory blooms in summer and bears fruit from late summer to mid-autumn. Currently, common chicory is popular in many countries as a delicious spice and diet food product. Roasted chicory root has long been one of Europeans' favorite coffee drinks. The juice prepared from the root of common chicory by adding milk and cream is included in the diet of children and people who cannot drink coffee due to their health as a substitute for coffee. Belgians stew common chicory with cheese and apples, Latvians prepare a cool drink from common chicory root with honey, lemon and apple juice. The leaves and branches of the special salad plant are used as a component of various salads, the young branches of the plant are boiled or added to the dough and cooked.

Collection of plants and its quality. Common chicory root is harvested in autumn in September-October. To do this, they are first dug with a shovel, sometimes plowed with a plow. After that, the roots are separated by hand, washed and dried. Before drying, the root is cleaned

from the unnecessary part of the stem. If the roots are thick and long, they are cut lengthwise and crosswise into several pieces and dried in a dryer at a temperature of 50-60⁰C.

Dried plant will have a wrinkled appearance. It is slightly brown on the outside, white or yellowish on the inside. It is a plant with a bitter taste rather than a specific smell. The above-ground part is prepared like any medicinal herb: the upper part of the sprig is collected during flowering, divided into separate pieces and dried in shady places with good air circulation.

Chemical composition. Common chicory root contains up to 60% inulin, 10-20% fructose, intibin glycoside (used in the pharmaceutical industry), as well as carotene, groups of vitamins B (B1, B2, B3), vitamin C, macro- and microelements (Na, K, Ca, Mg, P, Fe, etc.), there are organic acids, tannins, pectin, protein substances, resins. Sachratki root contains valuable substance inulin, which improves metabolism and normalizes the activity of the digestive system.

The use of common chicory in the treatment of various diseases.

Common chicory -(Cichorium intybus L.) medicinal plant is considered a valuable medicinal plant popular in folk medicine for a long time. Common chicory root was used in ancient Rome to improve digestion, and in Egypt it was used to prepare anti-venom for snake and spider bites. Common chicory was used in the treatment of diseases of the gastrointestinal tract and eyes, inflammation of the eyes and gout. In modern medicine, common chicory has found a wide variety of uses due to its beneficial medicinal properties (sedative, hypoglycemic, astringent, expectorant, diuretic, anti-inflammatory, antipyretic, anthelmintic).

Benefits of the plant for the digestive system.

Root decoction has been one of the best means for improving appetite and normalizing the functioning of the pancreas. In addition, it helps dissolve gallstones, has a bile driving effect, improves blood flow in the liver and its metabolic processes. Inulin obtained from the plant is a bifidostimulant, promotes the development of beneficial intestinal microflora, and strengthens the body's general immunity. The substances contained in sakhratki help reduce the inflammatory process of the stomach and intestinal mucosa. Due to the above properties, it is widely used in the prevention and treatment of gastric and duodenal ulcers, gastritis, dysbacteriosis, dyspepsia, constipation, liver and gallbladder diseases (cirrhosis, hepatitis, etc.). It is very useful for nervous system and cardiovascular system.

The juice made from the root of the medicinal plant Cichorium intybus L. is useful for people with hypertension, neurasthenia, depression, insomnia, and migraine, as there are no cases where it cannot be used as a caffeine-free coffee substitute.

The juice has a calming effect on the human nervous system due to the fact that it is rich in vitamin B (these vitamins are responsible for good mood, healthy sleep, energy and strength). At the same time, potassium-rich juice (necessary for the normal functioning of the heart) helps remove excess cholesterol from the blood, dilate blood vessels, and normalize the amplitude and rhythm of heart contractions. It is for this reason that it is useful for people suffering from atherosclerosis, tachycardia, diseases of the cardiovascular system, and other diseases to consume soft drink in their diet. The high amount of iron contained in Common chicory is used in the prevention and complex treatment of anemia.

Against diabetes and obesity. In medicine, it is considered valuable because it contains high molecular polysaccharide inulin in its root. It is inulin that helps to reduce the amount of sugar in the blood, improve metabolism and digestion, all these properties play a positive role in the prevention and treatment of diabetes and are effective in the fight against excess weight. It is

also used in complex treatment of skin diseases. Due to its bactericidal and anti-inflammatory effect, it can be used as a wound healing agent (infusion, decoction and alcohol tincture of the plant for seborrhea, allergic dermatitis, neurodermatitis, diathesis, eczema, chicken pox, psoriasis, pes, acne, furuncle, etc.). The use of thistle in everyday life has a significant positive effect in the treatment of spleen diseases, inflammatory diseases of the kidneys and kidney stones. In addition, regular consumption of the contents of the mushroom helps to cleanse people of toxins, radioactive substances and heavy metals.

Preparation of detox from common chicory root. Add 200 ml of boiling water to 1 spoonful of ground common chicory root, heat it after boiling for 10 minutes on low heat, then strain it. Drink 50 ml 3 times a day for diabetes. common chicory root decoction is used as an expectorant in diseases of the pancreas, gall bladder, liver (also in gallstone disease), as a diuretic in kidney diseases, improving digestion and treating metabolic diseases. Externally, it is used as baths, soaks and compresses for skin diseases and gout.

Common chicory root tincture. Pour 200 ml of boiling water over 2 teaspoons of crushed root, let it rest for 1-2 hours, cool and filter. The infusion is consumed 3-4 times a day. It is used in the treatment of diabetes.

Circumstances that cannot be used.

Patients suffering from vascular diseases, as well as varicose veins or hemorrhoids, should consult a doctor before consuming common chicory products in their daily diet.

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